

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: APOLLO****FIRST NAME: AFRICA SENDAHANGARWA****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 5%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 11

ACA 401D QUIZ

1. What does an academic essay seek to achieve?

An academic essay seeks to answer hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence.¹

The academic essay is a document that is developed by a student to achieve accreditation during a period of study.

An academic essay is a paper aimed at being published in an accredited journal.

This is an essay written and published by a member of the academia to achieve an academic title.

2. What is the meaning of plagiarism?

Using a direct quote of someone's work in your work without paraphrasing or summarizing.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: EUCLID University Press, 2024), 7.

Creating the impression in the reader's mind that the content is not your original ideas in a particular writing or academic paper.

Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.²

Cooperating with someone to write and submit a paper for academic purposes.

3. What is a Style guide, and why is it necessary?

A guide given by a lecturer to students on the format in which to write and produce academic papers in a university program.

A standard format of guidelines for writers to follow for consistency of the products from the same organization.³

A document that can be used to create specific documents to be transmitted to other organizations.

A document with strict guidelines to be followed when writing official documents.

4. In research and writing, what are the three kinds of sources of information?

The three kinds of sources in research and writing are human beings, printed materials like books and journals, and electronic sources.

Sources of information for researchers are categorized as primary or firsthand, secondary or secondhand, and tertiary or thirdhand sources.⁴

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 34.

³ Ibid, 41.

⁴ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th edition (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36–37.

- The three kinds of sources of information in research and writing are firsthand, secondhand, and thirdhand sources of information.
- Sources of information in research and writing are primary sources, secondary sources, and the internet.

5. What is a research argument?

- A research argument is assembled to answer five questions: what is the claim?**

What are the reasons for making the claim? What is the evidence that supports the reasons? Other points of view? And, what principle makes the reasons relevant to the claim?⁵

- A research argument is a kind of argument designed to win an academic debate or dispute.
- A research argument is a conversation based on reasoning between the arguing parties and reaching a sound conclusion.
- A research argument comprises well-thought-out and clever rhetoric strategies to persuade readers to accept your claims.

6. As a researcher, what are your two primary duties as far as citation is concerned?

- To cite all sources of information in the research and produce a bibliography or reference list.
- To give credit to all sources of data in the research and to use a consistent citation style in the whole document.

⁵ Ibid, 67.

- To give credit to sources of information, and the second duty is to reassure readers of the relevancy of the claims.

To get the facts right and to tell readers where the facts came from.⁶

7. What are the components of dissertation research?

- The introduction, statement of the problem, research questions, research design, variables, data analysis, research findings, and references.

Dissertation concept paper, dissertation prospectus, dissertation, and dissertation manuscript.⁷

- The preliminary pages, chapter one, chapter two, chapter three, chapter four, and the bibliography.

- The research problem, existing knowledge of the problem, research methods, and new findings on the problem.

8. What are the factors contributing to successful dissertation research?

- Consulting all types of data sources, good analysis skills, avoiding plagiarism, and subjecting your paper to peers for proofreading.

- Organizing the dissertation concept paper, the dissertation prospectus, the dissertation, and the dissertation manuscript.

Good communication, good planning, using an effective process for writing, attention to detail, openness to serendipity, and visualizing success.⁸

⁶ Ibid, 139.

⁷ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd Ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 9.

⁸ Ibid, 13–15.

- Clearly understanding the nature and process of dissertation research and the organization of dissertation documents.

9. What are the initial parts of a dissertation?

- The preliminary pages, the table of contents, the list of tables, the list of figures, and the introduction.
- The supervisory committee page, dedication, acknowledgments, table of contents, list of tables, figures, biography, and abstract.⁹**
- The preliminary pages, chapter one, and the introduction.
- The cover page up to the introduction.

10. Outline the logical flow and naming of chapters in a dissertation.

- Chapter One Introduction, Chapter Two Literature Review, Chapter Three Methods, Chapter Four Findings, and Chapter Five Analysis of Findings and Recommendations.
- Chapter One Introduction, Chapter Two Literature Review, Chapter Three Methods and Findings, and Chapter Four Analysis of Findings and Recommendations.
- Chapter One Introduction, Chapter Two Literature Review, Chapter Three Methodology and Research Approach, Chapter Four Findings, Chapter Five Analysis, Interpretation and Synthesis of Findings, and Chapter Six Conclusions and Recommendations.¹⁰**

⁹ Ibid, 24–26.

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 2nd ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019), 73–87.

- Chapter One Introduction, Chapter Two Literature Review, Chapter Three Methodology and Limitations, Chapter Four Findings, analysis and Interpretation, Chapter Five Conclusions and Recommendations.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.